

Poem

Vermilion

V. Bhavya Shree

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14277520

Vermilion
I don't believe in vermilion
She said ;
But I do ...
Mine was rigid.

Stockholm syndrome,
They burst into laughter.

Still I was
Cool as a cucumber,
For I believe in my folklore
And heritage,
Moreover
For me it is 'he'
A reminder of my nuptial bliss and nuptial vows.
(A jubilant face)

Are you a newly wed?
Yea I am.
(excited voice)

'It met with pearl of laughter.'

Why are you laughing?
A pure query...
again pearl of laughters left.

Mark my words;
This vermilion remains
Of my nuptial bliss and vows.

My foot.....
Indistinctive voices of frustrated faces
With frustrated vermilion,
Hold on their forehead
A reminder of their disappointed nuptial bliss and vows....

Glossary

1. Jubilant - feeling or expressing great happiness and triumph, elated
2. Nuptial - marital, wedded
3. Pearl of laughter - a burst of laughter
4. Stockholm syndrome - a coping mechanism for a captive or abusive situation
5. Vermilion - a red pigment and colour used by married women in India (sindoor)

Introduction of the Author

V. Bhavya Shree is a poet and teacher born in the beautiful village of Paravadukkam in Kasargod district. Following graduation and teacher training, she decided to pursue a career as an English language and literature teacher. She hopes and longs for the readers to have a deeper grasp of Marginalised sections and therefore, focused on herself as a bilingual poet of social and personal realism in minimalist poetry. Two of her realistic poems, "Funeral" and "Labour Room," were published in the online journal Holistic Pine, with the latter winning the "Readers Choice Award." Also featured as one of the five inspiring women shaping the literary landscape in holistic pine. She has marked her excellency by authoring poems in both English and Malayalam, which have been published on her blog <http://bhavyabharathii.blogspot.com> She is the daughter of Mr. Vasudevan Nambiar and Bharathi M. She is married to Mr. A. Krishna Kumar and they have a kid as well.

Author (s) Contribution Statement: Nil

Author (s) Acknowledgement: Nil

Author (s) Declaration: I declare that there is no competing interest in the content and authorship of this scholarly work.

The content of the article is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.